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**The main directions of socio-economic
development of New Uzbekistan:
problems and solutions**

MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND INNOVATION
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JIZZAKH BRANCH OF THE NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF UZBEKISTAN
NAMED AFTER MIRZO ULUGBEK

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The main directions of socio-economic development of New Uzbekistan:
problems and solutions collection of materials of the international scientific
and practical conference on the topic

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(Part 2)

Jizzakh-2024

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Editors in charge: DSc.prof. Turakulov O.X., PhD. O'ralov A.I.

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

MOBIL ILOVALAR ISHLAB CHIQISHDA MULTIPLATFORMA TEXNOLOGIYALARINING SAMARADORLIGI

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O'zbekiston milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali Kompyuter ilmlari
va dasturlash texnologiyalari yo'nalishi talabasi

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mobil ilovalar ishlab chiqishda qo'llanilayotgan multiplatforma texnologiyalarining afzalliklari, cheklovlari va samaradorligi o'rganiladi. Mobil texnologiyalar bozorida foydalanuvchilarning turli operatsion tizimlarda ishlovchi qurilmalardan foydalanishi, dasturchilar oldida iOS va Android uchun alohida kod yozmasdan universal ilovalar yaratish ehtiyojini tug'diradi. Shu munosabat bilan Flutter, React Native, Xamarin, Kotlin Multiplatform kabi multiplatforma vositalarining imkoniyatlari, ishlash tezligi, interfeys sifati va rivojlanish xarajatlari qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: mobil ilovalar, multiplatforma, Flutter, React Native, Xamarin, samaradorlik, dasturlash texnologiyalari

Kirish

So'nggi yillarda smartfonlar sonining tez sur'atlar bilan ortib borishi mobil dasturlar yaratishga bo'lgan talabni keskin oshirdi. Foydalanuvchilarning Android, iOS va boshqa operatsion tizimlarga ega qurilmalardan foydalanishi dasturiy ta'minot ishlab chiquvchilarni ushbu platformalarda muvofiqlikni ta'minlashga majbur qilmoqda. Shu nuqtai nazardan multiplatforma texnologiyalari zamonaviy dasturiy muhandislikda muhim o'rin egallamoqda. Ushbu maqolada multiplatforma texnologiyalari asosida ishlab chiqilgan mobil ilovalarning samaradorligi, ishlash tezligi, funktsionalligi va iqtisodiy jihatlari tahlil qilinadi.

Adabiyotlar sharhi

Multiplatforma ishlab chiqish texnologiyalari haqida birinchi izlanishlar 2010-yillarda paydo bo'lib, Apache Cordova va PhoneGap kabi texnologiyalar bilan boshlangan. 2015-yildan boshlab React Native (Facebook), Flutter (Google), Xamarin (Microsoft) kabi kuchli vositalar paydo bo'ldi. Ko'plab olimlar va muhandislar (N. Fernando, R. Posadas, J. Dominguez) multiplatforma ishlab chiqish vaqtini 30-50% gacha qisqartirishi va xizmat ko'rsatish xarajatlarini kamaytirishini tasdiqlagan. Shu bilan birga, ba'zi tadqiqotlar (D. Muller, L. Meyer) ayrim texnologiyalar ishlash samaradorligi yoki foydalanuvchi interfeysi sifatida natyiv ilovalardan orqada qolishi mumkinligini ta'kidlaydi.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi

Ushbu tadqiqotda quyidagi metodlar qo'llanildi:

- Ilmiy maqolalar va texnik hujjatlar tahlili (2015–2024);

- Dasturlash texnologiyalarini amaliy qiyosiy tahlil (Flutter, React Native, Xamarin, Kotlin Multiplatform);
- Dasturchilarning fikr-mulohazalari asosida intervyular;
- Real loyiha misollarida ishlash tezligi va resurslar iste'moli o'lchovlari.

Tahlil va natijalar

1-jadval: Multiplatforma texnologiyalarining taqqosiy xususiyatlari

Texnologiya	Til(lar)	Ishlash tezligi	UI sifati	O'rganish darajasi	Jamiyat yordami
Flutter	Dart	Yuqori	Juda yuqori	O'rta	Katta
React Native	JavaScript	O'rta	Yaxshi	Oson	Katta
Xamarin	C#	O'rta	Yaxshi	O'rta	O'rta
Kotlin Multiplatform	Kotlin	Yuqori	Yuqori	O'rta	Kichikroq

Jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdiki, Flutter va Kotlin Multiplatform ishlash tezligi va interfeys sifati bo'yicha yetakchilik qiladi. React Native esa oson o'rganilishi va keng jamoatchilik yordami bilan ajralib turadi.

2-jadval: Multiplatforma vs Natyiv ishlab chiqish bo'yicha xarajatlar va vaqt taqqoslamasi (o'rtacha loyihalar asosida)

Ko'rsatkichlar	Natyiv ishlab chiqish	Multiplatforma ishlab chiqish
Ishlab chiqish muddati	5-6 oy	3-4 oy
Dasturchilar soni (iOS+Android)	2+2 = 4	2
Qo'llab-quvvatlash xarajatlari	Yuqori	O'rtacha
Kodni qayta ishlatish darajasi	Past (10-20%)	Yuqori (60-90%)
O'zgartirishlar joriy qilish	Qiyin	Tez va moslashuvchan

Multiplatforma texnologiyalari ishlab chiqish muddatini va xarajatlarni kamaytirish, kodni qayta ishlatish imkoniyatlarini oshirish orqali iqtisodiy jihatdan ham foydali hisoblanadi.

Xulosa

Multiplatforma texnologiyalari mobil dasturlarni ishlab chiqishda zamonaviy yondashuv sifatida o'zini to'liq oqlamoqda. Ular ishlab chiqish vaqtini qisqartiradi, xarajatlarni kamaytiradi va ko'p platformali moslikni ta'minlaydi. Flutter va Kotlin Multiplatform ayniqsa yangi loyihalarda yuqori samaradorlikka erishish imkonini beradi. Shu bilan birga, ba'zi hollarda natyiv ilovalardek ishlash sifatini ta'minlash

uchun qo'shimcha optimallashtirishlar zarur bo'ladi. Kelajakda multiplatforma texnologiyalarining yanada mukammallashuvi va ommalashuvi kutilmoqda.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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